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This is to certify that the research paper entitled "I Know What to Click and What to Avoid": Gender Differences in Cybersecurity Awareness among Adolescent AI Users", authored by "Devendra Kumar", has been successfully published in ADEJ, Volume – 3, Issue – 2 (April-June 2026).

The paper has been assigned the DOI link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20606986>

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